

Supplementary material

The selected variables include temperature (BIO1, BIO2, BIO3), precipitation (BIO12, BIO15, BIO18), and elevation. This information highlights the ecological significance of each variable for *M. molossus*, particularly concerning its torpor and reproductive behaviors. Below is a summary of the rationale for each variable, which accompanies the table in the supplementary material:

In the case of temperature-related variables (BIO1, BIO2, BIO3), studies suggest that torpor and metabolic regulation are crucial for *M. molossus* survival in high-temperature environments, where even slight changes can significantly impact its energy behavior and ecology (Dechmann et al., 2011; O'Mara et al., 2017). Variations in mean diurnal temperature (BIO2) also influence the life cycle and development rates of insect populations, affecting prey availability for *M. molossus* (Chen et al., 2015).

For precipitation-related variables (BIO12, BIO15, BIO18), rainfall is a critical factor that influences the reproductive cycles of bats by increasing food availability during or after rainy periods (Heideman, 1995). Rainfall regulates explicitly the reproductive cycle of male *M. molossus*, with bimodal spermatogenic activity peaks in April and September (Soares et al., 2020), while females display two reproductive periods annually that coincide with the rainy season (Fabián; Marques, 1989). Precipitation also impacts foraging sessions, as *M. molossus* tends to avoid foraging in the rain (Dechmann et al., 2011; Racey et al., 1987).

This table in the supplementary material provides an organized view of the interactions between selected climatic and topographic variables and the hypotheses based on *M. molossus* natural history, per the reviewer's recommendation.

Table S1 - Supplementary Material - Relationship between the interactions of selected climatic and topographic variables and the hypotheses based on the natural history of *M. molossus*.

Variable	Type	Hypotheses Based on the Natural History of <i>M. molossus</i>
Mean annual temperature (BIO1)	Climatic Temperature	1. High temperatures may induce torpor, allowing <i>M. molossus</i> to maintain low metabolic rates in hot environments.
		2. Small fluctuations in temperature affect the species' energy behaviour and ecology.

Mean diurnal temperature variation (BIO2)	Climatic Temperature	1. They impact insects' development and life history, affecting prey availability for <i>M. molossus</i> .
		2. Temperature changes can modify degree-day accumulation, influencing foraging seasonality.
Isothermality (BIO3)	Climatic Temperature	1. It may influence metabolic rates and torpor behaviour in <i>M. molossus</i> in response to temperature variations.
		2. Variations in maximum and minimum temperatures can affect the species' reproductive cycle and foraging activity.
Annual precipitation (BIO12)	Climatic Precipitation	1. Precipitation increases food availability, influencing the reproduction and foraging of <i>M. molossus</i> .
		2. High precipitation periods are associated with male reproductive activity peaks.
Precipitation seasonality (BIO15)	Climatic Precipitation	1. Rain regulates the reproductive cycle of females, with two annual reproductive periods concentrated in the rainy season.
		2. Increased humidity and available insects during rain favour reproduction and reproductive success
Precipitation of the warmest quarter (BIO18)	Climatic Precipitation	1. Precipitation affects the quantity of flying insects, impacting the foraging efficiency of <i>M. molossus</i> .
		2. Climatic events resulting in rain may lead to missed foraging sessions, influencing food intake.
Elevation	Topographic	1. Elevation can influence temperature and precipitation, affecting the distribution and abundance of <i>M. molossus</i> .
		2. Changes in elevation may affect foraging and reproductive patterns due to microclimatic variations.

Supplementary material references

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